

Hamming Window-Based Discrete Wavelet Transform Technique for Enhancement of Electroencephalographic (EEG) Signal Processing

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ABSTRACT:

Electroencephalographic (EEG) signal is a biomedical signal generated by the electrical activity of the brain. Its waveform provides information about physiological state of the brain and can help medical experts make appropriate decisions on the condition and health of the brain. For the information in electroencephalographic signal to be extracted, it has to be analysed. This analysis can only be reliable if the EEG is devoid of noise. Incidentally, EEG signal is naturally mixed with, in addition to other biomedical signals, powerline interference. It therefore becomes necessary that the EEG which is signal of interest must be extracted from these other signals which constitute noise to it so that health care practitioners can make a reliable interpretation of the signal. In this work, a system for the reliable removal of powerline interference from Electroencephalographic signal based on discrete wavelet transform technique for the signal decomposition was modelled. A new shrinkage function called hamming window-based shrinkage soft thresholding (Ham-WSST) function was developed. An EEG signal was practically captured by measurement from Federal Medical Centre, Owerri and contaminated with 50Hz powerline noise. The sampling frequency is 1000Hz. Based on the new shrinkage function, decomposition level of 7 and daubechies 7(db7) mother wavelet, the denoising of the powerline noise was extensively performed. Seven different decomposition levels including levels 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 were used in sequence and the optimum decomposition level was found to be 7. The performance of the system was evaluated using power spectral density (PSD), signal to noise (SNR), mean square error (MSE) and maximum absolute error (MAE). The power spectral density based on the optimum decomposition level of 7 at 0.1 radian normalised frequency was 35.89 dB and signal to noise ratio was 42.26 dB. Also, mean square error was 0.00147 while the maximum absolute error was 0.1147. The developed shrinkage function was compared with two existing shrinkage functions of soft thresholding and hard thresholding functions and the developed function outperformed them as can be seen from the fact that the PSD, SNR, MSE, and MAE for soft thresholding shrinkage function are 37.93dB, 40.16 dB, 0.0127 and 0.17462 respectively while for the hard thresholding shrinkage function, the PSD, SNR, MSE and MAE are 39.58 dB, 38.46 dB, 0.00147 and 0.1147 respectively. Less PSD means more noise attenuation at the considered frequency instant. The contributions to knowledge in this work is to make window thresholding shrinkage function based on Hamming window a reliable alternative to other well-known wavelet coefficient shrinkage functions in using wavelet-based systems for practical purposes. The recommendation is that the system is very suitable for hospitals that handle neurological cases and should be deployed to such hospitals and EEG analysis centres.

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Keywords: EEG, FIR algorithm, public health, thresholding functions, thresholding shrinkage.

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INTRODUCTION

Electroencephalography (EEG) is electrical activity of the brain capture in a waveform whereas electroencephalogram (EEG) has to do with a test to evaluate the electrical activity in the brain so as to ascertain or diagnose the actual potential problems or brain disorders such as seizure disorders or epilepsy, injury to the head, encephalitis, brain tumour, encephalopathy, sleep disorders, memory problems, and brain stroke [1], Alzheimer's disease [2], epilepsy, dementia, checking whether a person in coma is brain dead, sleep disorders, mental health problems [3], epilepsy, brain tumour, stroke, sleep disorders, brain damage from head injury [4], epilepsy, sleep disorders, mental disorders [5], epilepsy or seizure disorders [6] and narcolepsy, sleep apnea syndrome, insomnia, parasomnia [7].

EEG signal in its natural form has very low amplitude, between the range of $10\mu V$ and $100\mu V$ (Dhaka and Saxena, 2023), $0.5\mu V$ and $100\mu V$ [8,9], $20\mu V$ and $100\mu V$ [5] and as such can easily be contaminated by interferences or noises which can be internal or external. The noise components technically referred to artifacts include eye movement signal (electrooculography), heart signal (electrocardiogram), muscle signal (electromyogram), baseline wander and powerline interference [10]. The range of frequency of a typical clinical EEG signal is from 0.01Hz to approximately 100Hz [11], 0.1Hz to 100Hz [12], 1.0Hz to about 100Hz [8], 0.5Hz to 100Hz [34], whereas that of powerline interference from mains power supply is 50/60Hz [7,8,13]. The source of the power line interference is electrode wires, light fluorescents and other acquisition equipment. The implication of the frequency ranges is that the frequencies of EEG signal and powerline noise component overlap. A reliable interpretation of EEG signal can only be possible when it is free of any artifacts. It therefore becomes imperative that these artifacts that corrupt the EEG signal must be removed and so, noise components must be removed so that the real appearance of the waveform can be determined and the clinical information content correctly extracted and interpreted. This work is therefore intended to denoise the EEG signal of powerline interference using discrete wavelet transform technique.

In reference study [14], discrete wavelet transform complex functions using five separate threshold functions were used. In the enquiry, using matlab 4000 samples of noisy EEG signals were acquired. The noisy EEG signals were broken down through decomposition to level 3 using analyzing wavelet functions like haar, Daubechies (Db5), and coiflets (Coif 5). The results obtained from the research showed that the combination of mother wavelet and threshold function that provided the best performance is Coif 5 mother wavelet with soft threshold function. The qualities of the signals denoised were evaluated with parameters such as mean square error (MSE) and signal to noise ratio (SNR). In reference study [15], a raw EEG signal that was taken from a patient whose rate of signal sampling is 256Hz with a 4 second time duration. After collection, artifacts comprising 50Hz powerline noise, EMG and baseline wandering were added to the collected EEG signal and recorded. Each of these recorded movements is called an epoch. A total of seven epochs were collected from each of four patients and that amounted to 28 epochs. After removing baseline wander, the algorithms of an IIR filter, a FIR filter and wavelet (Sym 29) were applied in sequence to this 28 epochs to obtain the filtered signals that were evaluated to obtain their signal to noise ratio values so as to quantify the most effective algorithm for the denoising. These results based on SNR show that wavelet transform technique is the best of the three techniques. Also, the average values of SNR of the filtered signal were calculated for the three algorithms and found to be 32.30dB, 33.55dB and 34.59 dB. The Average value of SNR for Sym 29 wavelet reported a higher bar for the tested epochs than those of IIR filter and FIR filters that reported lower bars. Lower bars of IIR and FIR filters means that the main signal was attenuated but other artifacts were still contained in the

denoised signal. Higher bar implies less attenuation of the main signal and better preservation of the main signal. This therefore suggests that the higher bar of Sym 29 wavelet is less attenuation of the main signal and better preservation of the EEG signal by Sym 29 wavelet than IIR and FIR algorithms. The research shows that the symlets 29 mother wavelet performance is the most compatible of the three algorithms with all tested EEG signals.

In this research work, emphasis is on powerline noise removal from the EEG signal. Different researchers have used different techniques to denoise EEG signal of powerline interference. The techniques include notch filtering [15,16], sparse representation based on denoising [2], Wavelet-ICA (independent component analysis) based denoising [9], adaptive noise cancelling [17], discrete wavelet transform denoising with hard thresholding and soft thresholding in sequence [14] and discrete wavelet transform [8,18]. In denoising EEG signal of powerline noise using discrete wavelet transform (DWT) the previous researchers used hard or soft thresholding shrinkage functions to shrink the coefficients of the EEG signal after decomposition with discrete wavelet transform. In this work a new shrinkage function called hamming window-based shrinkage soft thresholding (Ham-WSST) function is developed and applied on the decomposed EEG signal to enhance denoising quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the System

The general procedure in denoising EEG signal of noise using discrete wavelet approach as shown in Figure 1 has to do with the decomposition of the contaminated EEG signal with a chosen DWT mother wavelet of choice, applying soft shrinkage model on the coefficient of the signal and finally reconstructing the denoised signal.

Figure 1. Block Diagram Showing EEG Signal Denoising System

Wavelet as an analyzing function refers to an oscillatory decaying wave with limited time extent, with the ability to describe the information hidden within the time-frequency plane, with atoms of different time supports [7]. Wavelets are small localized wave functions which are confined in finite domains and used for the representation of data or a function that decay to zero instead of oscillating forever,. The equivalent mathematical conditions for a wavelet to exist are [19,20] as stated:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\Psi(w)|^2 dt < \infty \quad (1)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\Psi(t)| dt = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{|\Psi(w)|^2}{|w|} dw < \infty \quad (3)$$

Where $\Psi(w)$ is the Fourier transform of the function $\Psi(t)$. The function $\Psi(t)$ is called the mother wavelet. Equation (3) is known as [19-23] the admissibility condition.

The same way Fourier transform decomposes signals into its sine and cosine components, thereby obtain the correlation coefficients from the sinusoidal function, wavelet transform decomposes wavelet function into orthonormal functions thereby obtaining their correlation coefficients depending on the position and scale of the wavelet function.

Fourier transform has serious deficiency of time information after transformation to frequency domain. When observing a Fourier-transformed signal, it is not possible to tell when certain event took place. In the same way Fourier transform, which breaks down the frequency content in a function using sines and cosines, wavelet transform analyses the scale and position of function content with special function known as wavelet. If the mother function $\Psi(t)$ satisfies the conditions in (1) and (2) there exists an analyzing wavelet arising from the translation and dilations of the mother wavelet function and this analyzing wavelet is given [17,24] as

$$\Psi_{a,b}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|a|}} \Psi\left(\frac{t-b}{a}\right), \quad a, b \in \mathbb{R}, a \neq 0 \quad (4)$$

Recall that the parameter “a” is the scale and it measures the degree of compression or expansion of the scale. The parameter “b” is known as the translation parameter which determines or shows the time location of the wavelet. If $|a| < 1$, the wavelet function of equation (4) is the compressed (reduced in size) version of the mother wavelet. Once the analyzing wavelet is obtained, the wavelet transform of a real signal $x(t)$ is defined as

$$X(b, a) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Psi_{a,b}^*(t) x(t) dt \quad (5)$$

Where $\Psi_{a,b}^*$ is known as the complex conjugate of $\Psi_{a,b}(t)$. Substituting for $\Psi_{a,b}^*$ from equation (4) gives

$$X(b, a) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|a|}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Psi_{a,b}^* \frac{(t-b)}{a} x(t) dt \quad (6)$$

Where $\Psi^*(t)$ known as the complex conjugate of the mother wavelet function $\Psi(t)$.

Equation (6) which is the integral transformation of $\Psi_{a,b}(t)$ is known as the continuous wavelet transform of the function $x(t)$ [25] and can be identified as a convolution of the based function called the mother wavelet function and signal which is a translated and scaled version.

If the Fourier transform $\Psi(w)$ of function $\Psi(t)$ meets the admissibility condition

$$C_{\Psi} = \int_{-8}^8 \frac{|\Psi(w)|^2}{|w|} < \infty \quad (7)$$

then the original signal $x(t)$ can be obtained from the wavelet transform $X(b, a)$ by inverse wavelet transform formular [4] given as

$$x(t) = \frac{1}{C_{\Psi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} X(b, a) \Psi_{a,b}(t) da db \quad (8)$$

Where $\Psi_{a,b}(t)$ is the analyzing wavelet.

The analyzing wavelet in wavelet transform function can be discretised by using discrete values of the translation parameter “b” and the dilation parameter “a” to produce a discretised analyzing wavelet as shown in equation (9).

$$\Psi_{m,n}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_0^m}} \Psi\left(\frac{t - na_0^m b_0}{a_0^m}\right) \quad (9)$$

The signal $x(t)$ that has been transformed by wavelet transform using the discretised analyzing wavelet of (9) is called discrete wavelet transform (DWT) of the signal $x(t)$ as presented in equation (10)

$$X_{m,n} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_0^m}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \Psi^*\left(\frac{t - na_0^m b_0}{a_0^m}\right) dt \quad (10)$$

$$= \langle x(t), \Psi_{m,n}(t) \rangle \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) is the inner product of the functions $x(t)$ and $\Psi_{m,n}(t)$ as shown in equation (13). The original signal $x(t)$ can be determined from its discrete wavelet transform $X_{m,n}$ by the expression called inverse discrete wavelet transform (IDWT) as in equation (12) [26,27].

$$x(t) = A \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X_{m,n} \Psi_{m,n}(t) \quad (12)$$

Where “A” is a constant value for normalization

Inner product of the two functions $x(t)$ and $g(t)$ is defined as

$$\langle x(t) * g(t) \rangle = x(t) * g^*(t) \quad (13)$$

Where $g^*(t)$ is a complex conjugate of $g(t)$

Two functions are said to be orthogonal in nature if the inner product of the functions is zero. That is

$$\langle x(t) * g(t) \rangle = x(t) . g^*(t) = 0 \quad (14)$$

Three or more functions are said to be orthonormal if every two of the functions are orthogonal to each other. That is four functions as an example $g(t)$, $h(t)$, $x(t)$, $y(t)$ are orthonormal if

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g(t) * h(t) \rangle = 0, \langle g(t) * x(t) \rangle = 0, \langle g(t) * y(t) \rangle = 0, \langle h(t) * x(t) \rangle = 0, \\ \langle h(t) * y(t) \rangle = 0, \langle x(t) * y(t) \rangle = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

In decomposition the signal is separated into various components with each component having its own coefficients, by either discrete wavelet transform (DWT) function or continuous wavelet transform (CWT) function depending on which one that is applicable. In essences, what the wavelet transform function does is to separate the signal into two types of coefficient sequences. In order to do this a mother wavelet is first chosen and the level of decomposition N is also determined after which the signal is decomposed to that number of level N . The decomposition operation generates two types of coefficients; the detail coefficients and the approximation coefficients. These approximation coefficients A_k are generated by applying appropriate low pass filter and a down sampler on the wavelet-transformed signal and the detail coefficients D_k are generated by applying the appropriate high pass filter and a down sampler on the wavelet-transformed signal, where k varies from zero to infinity [28].

Modeling of the Window Shrinkage Function

Thresholding is a technique by which coefficients that constitute noise in a noisy signal are removed or reduced drastically after decomposition of the signal. There are two major kinds of thresholding functions, the hard thresholding and soft thresholding. For this work soft thresholding is used. Shrinkage is a technique for shrinking or further reducing the coefficients of the detail coefficients after thresholding. It is part of soft thresholding. The function of thresholding is to remove all coefficients below the threshold value and retain all coefficients equal or above the threshold value. But in soft thresholding the retained detail coefficients after thresholding are further modified by shrinking them to further remove noise component coefficients. First, the threshold value is determined by using the appropriate thresholding rule. Threshold rule is a method of determining the threshold value to be applied in the processing. There are various thresholding rules in existence such as universal, minimax, rigrsure and heursure thresholding rules. SURE standards for Stein's unbiased risk estimate. In this research the universal thresholding also known as sqtwolog rule will be used to determine the threshold value. The threshold value for universal thresholding or sqtwolog rule is given [22,29] as

$$T = \sqrt{2 \log(N)} \quad (16)$$

If normalization of data is not carry out with respect to noise standard deviation, then the threshold value is given [22,30-32] as

$$T = \sigma_n \sqrt{2 \log(N)} \quad (17)$$

where T is the value of threshold, N , the number of data samples and σ_n is the standard deviation of the noise component. The standard deviation of the noise σ is given by

$$\sigma_n = \frac{MAD}{0.6745} \quad (18)$$

where MAD represents the median absolute deviation of the coefficients of noise components.

After obtaining the threshold value, the next step is to shrink the detail coefficients using any appropriate shrinkage function.

The researcher's input in this work is to develop a new shrinkage function for the detail coefficients shrinkage. The window considered here is Hamming window function. The Hamming window function is as shown [33] in equation (3.70)

$$w(n) = 0.54 - 0.46 \cos \frac{2\pi n}{M-1}, 0 \leq n \leq M - 1 \quad (19)$$

Where $M=N+1$, the number of samples.

Decomposition detail coefficients are denoted by D_k , while the window coefficients are given by $w(k)$

where k and n vary from 0 to N , the number of samples. The new developed shrinkage function is as stated in (20)

$$D(w) = \begin{cases} \text{sgn}(D_k \cdot w(k)) (|D_k \cdot w(k)| - T) & |D_k \cdot w(k)| > T \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where $D(w)$ is the denoised signal coefficient sequence, T , the threshold value, $D_k \cdot w(k)$, the unshrunk product of detail coefficient and window coefficient sequence. Equation (20) is called hamming window-based shrinkage soft thresholding (Ham-WSST) function.

After applying shrinkage function on the decomposed EEG signal the output at this stage are denoised signal coefficients which should be reconstructed to obtain denoised analogue EEG signal which is approximately close to the original EEG signal. The up-sampling operator which samples the signal up by a factor 2 restores the samples removed by down sampling during decomposition. The synthesis filters of low pass filter and high pass filters are the reconstruction filters to ensure that the signal becomes analogue from discrete time form.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Signal Generation

The simulation parameters for the signal generations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The Parameters Used for Simulation

Factor	Quantity
Decomposition Level	7
Mother Wavelet	Daubechies 7 (db7)
Shrinkage Window	Hamming Window
Noise Type	Powerline
Iteration Number	11060
Threshold Rule	Sqtwolog
Signal	EEG

Results of Denoising Contaminated EEG Signal with the Developed Ham-WSST

In this section, an EEG signal contaminated by powerline noise was practically acquired by physical measurement from a patient in Federal Medical Centre, Owerri, Nigeria and loaded into a matlab environment. The contaminated EEG signal was decomposed to level 7 using mother wavelet of Daubechies 7 (db7) and thresholding was performed on it with the developed hamming window-

based shrinkage soft thresholding (Ham-WSST) function based on the universal threshold estimation rules, namely $\sqrt{2 \log n}$, threshold rule. Figure 2 depicts the acquired contaminated EEG signal while Figure 3 depicts the powerline noise assumed to have contaminated the EEG signal.

Figure 2. Contaminated Electroencephalographic (EEG)

Figure 3. Powerline Noise

The decomposed approximation coefficients for level 7 and that of detail coefficients from levels 1 to level 7 are depicted in figures 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 respectively and the results suggest that the function is physically realizable. The result of the approximation coefficients of Figure 4 also shows that the approximation coefficients sequence contains the wanted signal with the noise almost removed and this explains why no thresholding is performed on approximation coefficients. The detail coefficients contain more noise than the wanted signal as seen in Figures 5 to 11 and as such thresholding is performed on them to recover the components of the wanted signals in them.

Figure 4 Approximation Coefficient

Figure 5. Level 1 Detail Coefficients

Figure 6. Level 2 Detail Coefficients

Figure 7. Level 3 Detail Coefficients

Figure 8. Level 4 Detail Coefficients

Figure 9. Level 5 Detail Coefficients

Figure 10. Level 6 Detail Coefficients

Figure 11. Level 7 Detail Coefficients

The scheme in the developed thresholding technique is to use the inverted hamming window function coefficient sequence to shrink the amplitudes of the decomposed detail coefficients D_k of the contaminated EEG signal within the powerline noise region before further thresholding so that the noise is attenuated more effectively. The inverted hamming window function diagram for the first stage shrinking is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Inverted Hamming Window Function for First Stage Shrinkage

The frequency range of the EEG signal in question is from about 0.5Hz to about 100Hz. The powerline noise to be removed is 50Hz. At this 50Hz region, the window amplitude is zero; thus, the window will decimate the amplitude of the noise before second stage shrinkage. Figure 13 is a depiction of the denoised EEG signal based on the developed hamming window shrinkage function and sqtwolog threshold estimation rule.

Figure 13. EEG Denoised with Ham-WSST and Sqtwolog Threshold Rule at level 7

Determination of the Optimum Decomposition Level with db7 Mother Wavelet

Having determined the most effective threshold rule that works most effectively with the developed hamming window-based shrinkage soft thresholding (Ham-WSST) function to denoise EEG signal contaminated with powerline noise, the next step is to determine the optimum level of decomposition that will produce the best performance based on the developed shrinkage scheme. This is performed by varying the decomposition level below and above the applied trial level 7. The levels for consideration were 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9. Examining the appearances of the seven denoised signals it is observed that only levels 7 denoised the EEG signal most effectively and as such considered as optimum decomposition level.

In determining the attenuation level for the seven decomposition levels, the power spectral density responses was generated. Figures 14 is the power spectral density response of the EEG signal denoised with Ham-WSST at level 7. From the power spectral density plots, the PSD at 0.1 radian for each level is determined and presented in Table 2. The signal to noise ratio, the mean square error and maximum absolute error are also determined as presented in Table 3.

Table 2. PSDs at 0.1 Radian for Different Decomposition Levels with Ham-WSST

Level	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
PSD in dB	53.26	52.22	52.19	52.17	35.89	52.13	52.11

Table 3. SNR, MSE and MAE at Different Decomposition Levels with Ham-WSST

Level	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
SNR in dB	18.9458	19.1158	20.1762	21.445	42.26	21.6118	19.7486
MSE	0.0743	0.0743	0.0218	0.0209	0.00147	0.0290	0.0743
MAE	1.2523	0.9463	0.3770	0.3233	0.1147	0.3164	0.95451

Figure 14. PSD of EEG Denoised with Ham-WSST and Sqrtwolog Rule at Level 7

Figure 15. PSD of the Contaminated EEG Signal

It has earlier been established from table 2 PSDs of the denoised EEG signals as depicted that decomposition levels of 7 is the optimum decomposition level. Therefore, examining the PSD, SNR, MSE and MAE of the decomposition levels as depicted in table 2 and table 3, it can be deduced that decomposition level 7 is the most appropriate because it has highest noise attenuation with a PSD of 35.89 dB which implies more noise attenuation at 0.1 radian frequency instant, highest SNR of 42.26 dB which implies higher noise degradation with little degradation of wanted signal, and least MSE and MAE of 0.00147 and 0.1147 respectively.

Comparison of the Developed Ham-WSST and Other Thresholding Techniques

Using the optimum decomposition level of seven, threshold estimation rule of sqrtwolog, and mother wavelet of db7, performance of the developed technique and two main existing thresholding

techniques of conventional soft thresholding and hard thresholding techniques were compared. In order to realise this, the contaminated EEG signal of figure 1 was denoised with the developed technique of Ham-WSST, conventional soft thresholding and conventional hard thresholding. The power spectral density responses of the three denoised signals are presented as figures 16, 17 and 18 respectively. From the power spectral density responses of the three denoised signals, the PSD values of each signal at 0.1 radian normalized frequency was determined. The SNR, MSE and MAE for the three denoised signals were computed and presented in table 4.

Figure 16. Power Spectral Density of EEG Signal Denoised with Ham-WSST at Level 7

Figure 17. Power Spectral Density of EEG Denoised with Soft Thresholding at Level 7

Figure 18. Power Spectral Density of EEG Signal denoised Hard Thresholding at Level 7

Table 4. PSD, SNR, MSE and MAE of ECG Denoised with Ham-WSST, Soft and Hard

Thresholding Type	Developed Ham-WSST	Soft Thresholding	Hard Thresholding
PSD	35.89	37.93	39.58
SNR in dB	42.26	40.16	38.46
MSE	0.00147	0.0127	0.01894
MAE	0.1147	0.17462	0.19941

The results from Table 4 depicting the comparison of the developed Ham-WSST with the existing soft thresholding and hard thresholding shows that the developed Ham-WSST is better in removing the powerline noise at the normalized frequency of 0.1 radian because it has the least PSD value, implying better attenuation of the noise. The developed model also has the highest SNR of 42.26 dB, least MSE of 0.00147 and the least MAE of 0.1147, which confirms the developed Ham-WSST model outperforms the existing models of soft and hard thresholding techniques. Nevertheless, a narrow window will exhibit a superior performance because it will not do any useful amplitude degradation.

CONCLUSION

This work developed a new thresholding technique called Hamming window-based shrinkage soft thresholding (Ham-WSST) technique which was used to denoise EEG signal of powerline interference by wavelet transform and thresholding. The mother wavelet used in the decomposition is db7 and the initial decomposition level is 7. The performance of the technique was evaluated by comparing the attenuation of the powerline noise at 50Hz in the denoised EEG signals through their power spectral density responses. The attenuation values showed that the developed technique is effective. Other criteria for evaluation are signal to noise ratio, mean square error and maximum absolute error and each criterion confirmed the effectiveness of the developed technique. Variation of decomposition level was performed to ascertain the impact of level in the quality of denoising and the result is that the optimum decomposition level is level 7, which shows that decomposition level influences quality of denoising.

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